

Physical Constants and Geometry

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Abstract

By definition, physical constants do not change and are independent of the geometry of space and time. However, physicists have often incorporated geometrical features into physical constants.

In this work, I present two examples (Coulomb and Planck constants) where geometry was absorbed into the constants they introduced, and how later physicists separated this association. I also show that Isaac Newton did the same with the gravitational constant by embedding the factor 4π . Einstein's field equations incorporate the geometric factor through the term $8\pi G$, rather than separating it from the constant. In this paper I argue that the gravitational constant should be freed from its geometrical contribution.

Finally, I discuss how the lack of separation between constant and geometry in the gravitational constant affects the calculation of Planck length, time, energy, and mass.

1 Electrostatic Constant (k) and Planck Constant (h)

Electrostatic forces are given by Coulomb's law:

$$F = k \frac{q_1 q_2}{r^2}, \quad (1)$$

where k is the electrostatic constant.

The appearance of the term r^2 reflects the spherical spreading of photons, since the surface of a sphere is

$$S = 4\pi r^2. \quad (2)$$

Thus, the geometry (4π) is absorbed into the constant k . Later, physicists replaced k with

$$k = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0}, \quad (3)$$

where ϵ_0 is the vacuum permittivity. The law can be rewritten as

$$F = \frac{q_1 q_2}{4\pi\epsilon_0 r^2} = \frac{q_1 q_2}{\epsilon_0 S}. \quad (4)$$

Figure 1: Illustration of spherical surfaces: $4\pi r_1^2$ and $4\pi r_2^2$. The factor 4π originates from the geometry of the sphere.

Similarly, in quantum mechanics, Planck introduced his famous relation

$$E = h\nu, \quad (5)$$

with the Planck constant h . The reduced Planck constant $\hbar = h/(2\pi)$ is used because quantization is related to the length of the perimeter rather than to surface areas.

2 Newton's Gravitational Constant (G)

Newton's gravitational law is analogous to Coulomb's law:

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}. \quad (6)$$

This can be rewritten as

$$F = \frac{G'}{S} m_1 m_2, \quad (7)$$

where

$$G' = 4\pi G = 8.386896 \times 10^{-10} \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-2}. \quad (8)$$

Unlike in electromagnetism, this modification was never adopted. Einstein, in general relativity, included $8\pi G$ in his field equations:

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{8\pi G}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}. \quad (9)$$

Using the modified constant G' , this becomes

$$R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu} R = \frac{2G'}{c^4} T_{\mu\nu}. \quad (10)$$

3 Implications for Planck Units

While the equations are computationally equivalent for gravity, the distinction between constants and geometry has implications for Planck units.

Planck defined natural units using \hbar , c , and G :

$$l_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^3}}, \quad (11)$$

(12)

$$t_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar G}{c^5}}, \quad (13)$$

(14)

$$E_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c^5}{G}}, \quad (15)$$

(16)

$$m_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}. \quad (17)$$

These are fundamental units because they arise solely from constants of nature. However, if G' is used instead of G , the values shift significantly.

Quantity	Symbol	Using \hbar, c, G	Using \hbar, c, G'	Unit
Planck length	l_p	1.61625×10^{-35}	5.72923×10^{-35}	m
Planck time	t_p	5.39124×10^{-44}	1.91108×10^{-43}	s
Planck energy	E_p	1.95610×10^9	5.51871×10^8	J
Planck mass	m_p	2.17645×10^{-8}	6.14039×10^{-9}	kg

For example, the Planck energy marks the expected unification scale of gravity with the other fundamental forces.

We must recalculate the Planck's constants, as we already have done for the Planck charge :

$$q_p = \sqrt{4\pi\epsilon_0\hbar c} = 5.29076 \times 10^{-19}, \quad (18)$$

which is about 3.3 times the electron charge, in contrast with the older definition

$$q_p = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{\epsilon_0}} = 1.87555 \times 10^{-18}, \quad (19)$$

corresponding to about 11.7 times the electron charge.

4 Conclusion

The gravitational constant should be freed from its geometrical contribution, just as Coulomb's constant and Planck's constant were. This would modify the formulation of Newton's and Einstein's laws, and at the same time, it would redefine the values and physical meaning of Planck units.

References

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